

High modulated soliton power propagation interaction with optical fiber and optical wireless communication channels

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ABSTRACT

This paper has presented high modulated soliton power transmission interaction with optical fiber and optical wireless communication channels at flow rate of 40 Gbps and 20 km link range. The proposed modulation schemes are continuous phase frequency shift keying (CPFSK), Quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM), differential phase shift keying (DPSK), frequency shift keying (FSK), pulse amplitude modulation (PAM), minimum shift keying (MSK), and optical quadrature phase shift keying (OQPSK). CPFSK has presented better performance than other proposed modulation schemes for both optical fiber and optical wireless communication channels. The enhancement of optical signal/noise ratio at fiber/wireless channel, received electrical power and signal/noise ratio at optical receiver with increase of bits per symbol for different proposed modulation schemes except for CPFSK scheme. Therefore it is evident that CPFSK modulation scheme is more efficient and better performance than other modulation schemes for different communication channels. The obtained results are simulated with optisystem program version 13.

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1. INTRODUCTION

They have outlined the soliton molecule concept. The output field amplitude for two, three soliton molecules are measured in the presence of spatial light modulator [1-9]. The Soliton transmission performance in optical wired link is investigated in the presence of nonlinear conditions and micro ring resonators [10-15]. They have reviewed optical soliton pulses in the nonlinear effects. Bit error rate is measured for free space optics channel for 2.5 Gb/s transmission [3]. They have presented the analysis of high order soliton interaction effects on fiber channel [16-22]. They have examined femto-second Soliton transmission in erbium doped fiber amplifiers media. They have found Inhomogeneous Hirota Maxwell Bloch equation for solving the exact soliton managed for dispersion control with the variations of nonlinear effects parameters and dispersion parameter effects [23-26]. They have also discussed the effect of amplified periodic pulse distribution and soliton pulse compression when they have into account the soliton signal stability in special cases [27-37]. They have reviewed the soliton order propagation system for ultra high system transmission capacity for possible transmission bit rate of 80 Gb/s for possible transmission length of 20000 km. operating signal wavelengths that are available are 1300 nm, 1550 nm [38-45].

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

Figure 1 outlines the view of proposed model for this study. Pseudo random bit sequence generator generates sequence of bits usually bit sequence of 0's and 1's. The generated bit sequence is directed to electrical modulators and optical Sech pulse generators for modulating and reshaping soliton pulses with high power level of 2 W, and operating frequency of 1550 nm. The modulated electrical signal from electrical modulators and high optical soliton signal power are directed to electro optic modulator such as Mach Zehnder modulator for modulating the electro optic signal. The modulated optical signal is then distributed through fork element to two path, one is optical fiber channel and the second is optical wireless communication channel. The two optical signal are then directed to APD to convert the optical signal to light signal. The converted electrical signal directed to low pass bessel filter (LPBF) in order to removed unwanted signal from the original signal. The output signal from LPBF is then forward to 3R regenerator for retiming, regeneration and reshaping.

WDM analyzer measures signal power, noise power, gain, noise figure, and optical signal/noise ratio for both fiber/wireless communication channel. Eye diagram analyzer tests the max Q factor level, signal/noise ratio and min bit error rate at the receiver side.

Figure 1. Proposed simulation model

3. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS WITH DISCUSSIONS

We have simulated high modulated soliton power interaction with both optical fiber and optical wireless communication channels. There are different proposed modulation techniques are employed in the study, that are namely CPFSK, DPSK, PAM, QAM, FSK, OQFSK, and MSK. Optical signal/noise ratio at fiber/wireless communication channel is measured. As well as received electrical power and SNR at optical receiver are measured as in the series of Figures 2-14 based on variables in Table 1. Figure 2 has outlined OSNR at fiber/wireless channel, SNR at optical receiver and bits per symbol based CPFSK modulation technique. As bits per symbol increases leading to OSNR, and SNR decrease. It is observed that from Figure 3, the effects of the increase of bits per symbol on the received power at optical receiver for both fiber/wireless communication channel.

Table 1. Variable for proposed work [14]

Optical Sech pulse generator	
Parameter	Value
Operating wavelength	1550 nm
Input power	2 W
Electrical modulators	
Bits/symbol	2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64
Frequency separation	10 MHz
Frequency	250 GHz
Optical Wireless channel (OWC)	
Attenuation (clear condition)	0.2 dB/km
Range	20 Km
Tx./Rx. Aperture diameter	30 cm
Beam divergence	2 mrad
Fiber channel	
Loss	0.2 dB/Km
Dispersion	16.75 ps/nm/Km
Range	20 Km
MZM	
Extinction ratio	30 dB
Symmetry factor	-1
APD	
Responsivity	1 A/W
Dark current	10 nA
LPBF	
Loss	0 dB
Depth	100 dB

Figure 2. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel and SNR at optical receiver with bits/symbol based CPFSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 3. Received electrical power at photodetector with bits/symbol based CPFSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 4. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel and SNR at optical receiver with bits per symbol based DPSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 5. Received electrical power at photodetector with bits/symbol based DPSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 6. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel and SNR at optical receiver with bits/symbol based FSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 7. Received electrical power with bits/symbol based FSK modulation scheme for fiber/wireless channel

Figure 8. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel and SNR at optical receiver with bits/symbol based QAM modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 9. Received electrical power at photodetector against bits/symbol based QAM modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

On the other hand, it is observed that from Figures 4 and 5, the positive effects of increasing bits per symbol based DPSK modulation scheme on the optical signal/noise ratio (OSNR) at fiber/wireless channel, signal/noise ratio (SNR), and electrical received power at optical receiver. In the same way, it is clear that from Figures 6 and 7, the positive effects of increasing bits per symbol based FSK modulation scheme on the OSNR at fiber/wireless channel, SNR, and received electrical power at optical receiver. Figure 8 has presented the relation between OSNR, SNR and bits per symbol based QAM modulation scheme. As bits per

symbol increases, leading to increase in both OSNR and SNR. On the other hand, the negative effects of increasing bits per symbol based QAM modulation scheme on electrical received power as clarified in Figure 9. Figure 10 has presented the relation between OSNR, signal to noise ratio and bits/symbol based PAM modulation scheme. As bits/symbol increases, leading to increase in both OSNR and SNR. On the other hand, the negative effects of increasing bits per symbol based PAM modulation scheme on electrical received power as clarified in Figure 11. As shown in Figure 12, the complete comparison for OSNR performance parameter for different proposed modulation techniques based both fiber/wireless communication channels. It is clear that CPFSK is more efficient and better performance than other proposed modulation schemes for both fiber/wireless channel.

Figure 10. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel and SNR at optical receiver with bits/symbol based PAM modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 11. Received electrical power at photodetector with bits/symbol based PAM modulation scheme for fiber/wireless communication channel

Figure 12. OSNR at fiber/wireless channel against various modulation schemes at optimum conditions

Figure 13. Electrical received power at optical receiver versus various modulation schemes at optimum conditions

Figure 14. SNR at optical receiver against various modulation schemes at optimum conditions

It is clear that CPFSK is more efficient in optical wireless channel than fiber channel. As well as the electrical received power is upgraded by using CPFSK, PAM, FSK modulation schemes for optical wireless channel that fiber channel as clarified in Figure 13. Moreover, SNR is upgraded using CPFSK, DPSK, and PAM modulation schemes for optical fiber channel than optical wireless channel as clarified in Figure 14.

4. CONCLUSION

Various modulation schemes are employed with high soliton power transmission over fiber and wireless communication channels. It is found that the higher bits per symbol for different proposed modulation techniques, the higher OSNR, electrical received power, and SNR except for CPFSK modulation scheme. CPFSK modulation scheme has clarified better performance and more efficient than other proposed modulation techniques for both fiber/wireless communication channels. The received electrical power at optical receiver is enhanced by using proposed modulation techniques in optical wireless channel than fiber channel. It is evident that CPFSK, PAM, and DPSK are efficient in upgrading SNR at receiver for fiber channel over wireless channel. OSNR is enhanced by using CPFSK modulation scheme by enhancement percentage ratio ranges from 7.18 % to 45.45 % for optical fiber channel, and 28.45 % to 57.6 % for optical wireless communication channel. Electrical received power level is upgraded by using CPFSK modulation scheme that ranges from 6.4 % to 16.85 % in optical fiber channel, and its percentage enhancement ratio in received power level ranges from 9.58 % to 36.23 % for optical wireless communication channel. The percentage enhancement ratio in SNR value for CPFSK modulation over other proposed modulation techniques for optical fiber communication channel ranges from 8 % to 37.39 % and for optical wireless communication channel ranges from 15.6 % to 17.63 %.

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